

1 *Original Scientific Research Paper*

2 **Nitrogen Scavenging from Amino Acids and Peptides in the Model Alga**
3 ***Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*. The Role of Extracellular L-Amino Oxidase**

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16 **Keywords:** Algae; *Chlamydomonas*; Extracellular L-amino acid oxidase; LAAO; LAO1; Amino acids;
17 Peptides; Nitrogen mineralization.

18

19 **Abstract**

20 Phytoplankton live under constantly changing environments in which concentrations of inorganic
21 nitrogen can be limiting but organic nitrogen sources (urea, amino acids or peptides) are available.
22 Understanding how algae, as primary producers, assimilate organic nitrogen is of eco-physiological
23 importance although such studies are rare. Given genetic tractability, the green microalga
24 *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* is an excellent model system for elucidating amino acid assimilation by
25 algal species. This alga can extracellularly deaminate most amino acids using a L-Amino acid Oxidase
26 (LAO1), which generates ammonium that can then be taken up as a source of nitrogen. In this work,
27 we have used *lao1* mutant strains to investigate the impact of the absence of this enzyme on *C.*
28 *reinhardtii* growth using amino acids and di-/tri-peptides as sole nitrogen sources. Our results show
29 that LAO1 enzyme is crucial for growth on most proteinogenic amino acids and peptides by this alga.
30 We present findings from an analysis of algal genomes that reveal a new evolutionary branch for algal
31 L-amino acid oxidase genes (ALAAO) that includes Rhodophyta, Alveolata, Heterokonta,
32 Haptophyta, and Dinophyta species. Interestingly, *C. reinhardtii* appears to be the only green algal
33 that contains an ALAAO homolog, and we present a hypothesis about the possible origins of ALAAO
34 genes in algae based on a comparative analysis of currently available and assembled algal genomes.

35

36 1. Introduction

37 Inorganic nitrogen is often the most abundant form of nitrogen in marine and freshwater
38 systems, with concentrations that can regularly change spatially or temporarily reach low levels,
39 while organic nitrogen sources like urea and free amino acids are often at higher concentrations
40 (reviewed by Berman and Bronk, 2003). In many aquatic systems, terrestrial leaking and runoff are
41 important inputs of organic nitrogen. Sewage and other anthropogenic activities lead to significant
42 infusions of organic nitrogen into rivers that are eventually transported to estuarine and coastal
43 waters. These organic inputs into water systems have dramatically increased over the last century
44 due to industrial growth and global warming, and have great impact on the biodiversity of associated
45 ecosystems (Berman and Bronk, 2003; Seitzinger and Sanders, 1997, 1999; Vaquer-Sunyer et al., 2015).
46 Although bacteria have long been considered to be the dominant consumers of organic nitrogen,
47 many phytoplankton species have been shown to also use organic nitrogen as evidenced during algal
48 blooms (Berman and Bronk, 2003; Fan and Glibert, 2005; Ramûnas et al., 2002; Seitzinger and Sanders,
49 1999). Thus, primary producers may compete with other heterotrophic organisms like bacteria for
50 organic nitrogen, which should be factored into models of ecosystem balance.

51 The green microalga *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii* has served as a model organism for
52 physiological studies for more than fifty years (Harris, 2001) and nitrogen metabolism in this alga has
53 been one of the most extensively studied of any alga (Sanz-Luque et al., 2015). This alga preferentially
54 assimilates inorganic nitrogen over other sources (Fernandez and Galvan, 2008). Under inorganic
55 nitrogen deficiency, *C. reinhardtii* can grow on organic nitrogen sources such as urea, purines and
56 amino acids. L-arginine is the only reported amino acid that is imported by a high affinity transporter
57 in *C. reinhardtii* (Kirk and Kirk, 1978a). Once intracellular, L-arginine is deaminated by an arginine
58 deiminase (ADI), producing ammonium is incorporated into carbon skeletons by the GS-GOGAT
59 cycle (Fernandez and Galvan, 2007). *C. reinhardtii* also bears a periplasmic L-amino acid oxidase
60 encoded by the gene *LAO1* that deaminates a wide range of L-amino acids according to the reaction:

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64 The resulting ammonium is then imported into the cell by ammonium transporters (AMTs); the α -
65 keto acids are not further metabolized and remain extracellular (Muñoz-Blanco et al., 1990). The *LAO1*
66 protein is highly expressed during nitrogen starvation but is repressed in the presence of ammonium
67 (Vallon et al., 1993). An intracellular *LAO1* homolog exists and is encoded by the gene *LAO3* (Vallon
68 and Spalding, 2009).

69 L-Amino Acid Oxidases (LAAOs, EC 1.4.3.2.) are widely distributed in nature and are present
70 in diverse organisms including bacteria (Faust et al., 2007), fungi (Aurich et al., 1972; Nuutinen et al.,
71 2012), algae (Fujisawa et al., 1982; Rees and Allison, 2006; Vallon et al., 1993), fishes (Kitani et al., 2007),
72 the sea hare (Yang et al., 2005), mammals (Nagaoka et al., 2009; Sun et al., 2002), and in snake venom
73 (Bordon et al., 2015; Tõnismägi et al., 2006). LAAOs catalyze a similar reaction in different organisms
74 with similar structures that may derive from a common evolutionary origin but evolved to cope with
75 different physiological functions in distinct groups (Campillo-Brocal et al., 2015; Macheroux et al.,
76 2001). While the major role of some LAAO enzymes has been suggested to be defence against
77 pathogens by H_2O_2 generation (Kasai et al., 2015), it has also been shown that fungal and algal LAAOs
78 help to scavenge nitrogen from amino acids (Nuutinen and Timonen, 2008; Piedras et al., 1992).
79 Consistent with this function in algae and fungi, LAAO enzymes show broad substrate specificity and
80 are induced under nitrogen-limiting conditions (Davis et al., 2005; Sikora and Marzluf, 1982; Vallon

81 et al., 1993). LAAOs may provide an ecological advantage in instances where inorganic nitrogen is
82 limiting, and organic nitrogen is otherwise available. However, information about how algae use
83 amino acids as a nitrogen source is in general poorly understood.

84 In this work we used *C. reinhardtii* *lao1* mutants to study the impact of extracellular LAAO on
85 nitrogen scavenging from amino acids and peptides. We also analyzed LAAO genes from available
86 sequenced algal genomes to gain insights into the evolutionary origins of L-amino acid oxidase-based
87 mineralization of amino acids/peptides. We discuss three independent pathways for nitrogen
88 acquisition from amino acids/peptides in algae: (1) amino acid transport, (2) extracellular amine
89 oxidation, and (3) bacterial metabolic complementation.

90

91 2. Materials and methods

92 2.1 Strains

93 The *C. reinhardtii* *lao1* mutant LMJ.RY0402.044073 and its parental strain CC-5325 were
94 obtained from the *Chlamydomonas* Resource Center (<https://www.chlamycollection.org/>). This *lao1*
95 mutant contains a putative CIB gene cassette insertion at the *Cre12.g551352* locus, corresponding to
96 the *LAO1* gene (Li et al., 2016). This cassette contained a paromomycin resistance marker gene. We
97 confirmed this mutant genotype via colony PCR using primers that flank the regions of insertion
98 (*LAO1F*: 5'-TCG AAG CAA GTA CAC GCA AC-3' and *LAO1R* 5'-AAC TGT GGG AGT GTG GGA AG-
99 3'), and in combination with primers matching the inserted cassette (Li et al. 2016) (*CIB* 5' (5'-GCA
100 CCA ATC ATG TCA AGC CT-3')-*LAO1F* and *CIB* 3' (5'-GAC GTT ACA GCA CAC CCT TG-3')-*LAO1R*).
101 Amplicons with expected sizes were sequenced (SCAI Sequencing Facility, University of Córdoba) to
102 confirm the insertion of the cassette in the *LAO1* gene (Phytozome ID (v4 genome): *Cre12.g551300.t1.1*).
103 The corroborated flanking region sequences were: 5' flanking region: 5'- CAC GAA GCC TGT GTG
104 GGT GGT GCG TGC GTG -3'; and 3' flanking region: 5'- GTG ACG TTC GTG GAG GAG CTG ACA
105 AAG CTG-3'). In referencing the experimentally verified cDNA sequence for *LAO1* (NCBI accession
106 *U78797.1*) (Vallon and Wollman, 1997), we verified that the current *C. reinhardtii* genome annotation
107 (Phytozome v5.5; <https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/>) incorrectly splits *LAO1* into two gene models,
108 *Cre12.g551352.t1.1* and *Cre12.g551253.t1.1*.

109 The genetic cross between wild-type CC-1690 and *lao1* mutant was performed by the random
110 spore plating method (Levine and Ebersold, 1960). One hundred randomly selected colonies were
111 plated on TAP agar (1.6%) plates containing either ammonium (8 mM) or ammonium and
112 paromomycin (25 µg·mL⁻¹) as sole nitrogen source for segregant analysis.

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114 2.3 Growth experiments on L-amino acids and peptides

115 *C. reinhardtii* pre-cultures were grown on Tris-Acetate-Phosphate (TAP) medium as previously
116 described (Gorman and Levine, 1965), supplemented with 8 mM of ammonium chloride (TA medium)
117 for 2-3 days (mid-log growth phase) at 23 °C under continuous light with agitation. Cells were
118 harvested by centrifugation (3 min at 3,000 g) and washed three times with TAP medium without
119 nitrogen. Cells were transferred to TAP medium containing the indicated L-amino acid (8 mM) or
120 peptide (4 mM) as the sole nitrogen source, with the exception of L-tyrosine, which was used at 2 mM
121 due to poor solubility. The initial cell concentration was A_{750} of 0.025 for liquid culture tests. For
122 growth tests on solid media, 5 µL of each cultures with A_{750} of 0.125 were plated. Final cell

123 concentrations of liquid cultures were determined using a cell counting (Sysmex Microcellcounter F-
124 500).
125

126 2.4. Gene expression quantification

127 *C. reinhardtii* CC-1690 cells were grown in liquid TA medium for 3 days with continuous light
128 and agitation. Cultures were harvested by centrifugation (2 min at 3,000 rpm) and washed twice with
129 MM without nitrogen (M-N). Cells were transferred to fresh M-N media supplemented with 4 mM of
130 ammonium chloride, potassium nitrite or potassium nitrate, to study the effect of different nitrogen
131 sources. After 10 hours, cells were harvested by centrifugation (2 min at 2,000 g), resuspended in lysis
132 buffer (50 mM Tris·HCl pH 8, 300 mM NaCl, 5 mM EDTA pH 8 and 2% SDS) and frozen at -80 °C.
133 Samples were thawed and RNA extracted using a standard phenol-chloroform extraction protocol
134 (Sambrook, Maniatis, & Fritsch, 1989). Total RNA was precipitated overnight with 4 mM LiCl,
135 quantified spectrophotometrically, and run on a gel to check RNA integrity. One ng of total RNA was
136 used to synthesize cDNA using iScript Reverse Transcriptase (Bio-Rad, Madrid, Spain). The resulting
137 cDNA was used to quantify the relative *CreLAO1* expression by qPCR using SsoFast EvaGreen
138 Supermix (Bio-Rad, Madrid, Spain) and specific primers for *CreLAO1* gene expression (LAO1QC1: 5'-
139 GAG ACT GTG ATG CCC AAA AAG TG-3'; LAO1QR1: 5'-GCT TGC CCA GGC CGC GAA TGG AA-3')
140 (Wei et al., 2014). Simultaneously, we measured the gene expression of ubiquitin ligase, a
141 housekeeping gene control for which expression was reported to be constitutive under the conditions
142 used in this work (González-Ballester et al., 2004). The mixed reactions were run and detected using
143 the MyiQ2 detection system (Bio-Rad, Spain) with the following conditions: initial denaturation for 2
144 min at 98°C, 5 s of denaturation at 98°C (40 cycles) and 10 s of annealing and extension at 60°C. All
145 qPCR runs contained two technical replicates of reactions with the same cDNA sample for each of the
146 three biological replicates, along with no-DNA negative controls. The Ct values obtained were
147 normalized to the housekeeping gene control and expressed as fold-changes ($2^{-\Delta Ct}$, where $\Delta Ct = Ct_{\text{sample}}$
148 $- Ct_{\text{control}}$).

149 2.5 Phylogenetics analysis

151 Different genome resources were used to identify LAO1 orthologs: NCBI
152 (<https://blast.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/Blast.cgi>), the JGI Genome Portal (<https://genome.jgi.doe.gov/portal/>)
153 and Phytozome (<https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/>). Putative subcellular location was also analyzed for
154 each ortholog using the PredAlgo program, tailored to algae (Tardif et al., 2012).

155 Evolutionary trees of LAOs and other enzymes with amine oxidase activity were constructed
156 using the Maximum Likelihood method and default settings in MEGA7 (Kumar et al., 2016).
157 Alignments were performed using the Clustal method, and evolutionary distances were computed
158 using the Poisson correction model (Zuckerandl and Pauling, 1965). The bootstrap consensus tree
159 was inferred from 500 replicates (Felsenstein, 1985). This analysis involved 60 amino acid sequences
160 (Supplemental Table S1).

161 3. Results and discussion

162 3.1 The impact of LAO1 on the use of amino acids and peptides in *Chlamydomonas reinhardtii*.

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166 LAAOs have a role on L-amino acid catabolism. In fact, in natural waters where algae are present,
 167 LAAOs are proposed to alter amino acid distributions (Palenik and Morel, 1990a). The *C. reinhardtii*
 168 genome contains two LAAO genes: *LAO1*, located on chromosome 12 that encodes the periplasmic
 169 LAAO (NCBI protein ID: AAB97101.1); and *LAO3*, located on chromosome 5 that encodes a putative
 170 intracellular LAAO (NCBI protein ID: XP_001700756.1). The *LAO1* enzyme has been more extensively
 171 characterized and shown to generate ammonium from L-amino acids, which *C. reinhardtii* uses for
 172 growth, while the corresponding α -keto acid byproduct is not assimilated (Muñoz-Blanco et al., 1990).
 173 The purified *LAO1* protein was shown to have activity over a broad range of proteinogenic amino
 174 acids (Vallon et al., 1993). The cDNA corresponding to the catalytic subunit was verified by cloning
 175 (Vallon and Wollman, 1997), and *LAO1* gene expression is a hallmark cell response to nitrogen
 176 deprivation (Bulté and Wollman, 1992; Vallon et al., 1993).

177 Here we analyzed nitrogen scavenging from amino acid and peptides by *C. reinhardtii* strains
 178 containing or lacking a functional *LAO1* gene. The *C. reinhardtii* *lao1* insertional mutant (strain
 179 *LMJ.RY0402.044073*) was first verified for the integration of the paromomycin resistant cassette in
 180 *LAO1* gene (Figure 1). According to the cDNA sequence (*U78797.1*) (Vallon and Wollman, 1997) and
 181 the *LAO1* transcript model (Phytozome ID (v4 genome), *Cre12.g551300.t1.1*) the cassette is integrated
 182 in the exon seven of *LAO1*.

183 **Figure 1.** A, Schematic view of *LAO1* gene with the insertion site of the CIB cassette in *lao1* mutant.
 184 Primers used for characterization by amplification are indicated by black arrows. B, *lao1* mutant
 185 characterization by PCR. Primer sequences and PCR specifications for amplification are indicated in
 186 *Materials and Methods* section. Expected fragments for parental strain (CC-5325) and *lao1* mutant
 187 (*LMJ.RY0402.044073*) are indicated by asterisks. (-) indicates negative controls without DNA template.

189 To further confirm that the paromomycin resistant phenotype was due to a unique integration
 190 event in *LAO1*, a genetic cross between the *lao1* mutant (mt-) and a wild-type strain CC-1690 (Sager
 191 21gr, mt+) was performed. Of the segregants, 51% were resistant to paromomycin, suggesting a single
 192 integration event. Six paromomycin-resistant and six paromomycin-sensitive representative
 193 segregants were chosen to test growth on L-alanine or L-serine. As shown in Figure 2, all
 194 paromomycin-resistant segregants and parental *lao1* mutants showed impaired growth on these
 195 amino acids. In contrast, all the paromomycin-sensitive segregants and wild-type parental strains
 196 were able to use the L-amino acids for growth.

197
 198 **Figure 2.** Growth phenotypes of segregants from a genetic cross between the *C. reinhardtii* *lao1*
 199 *LMJ.RY0402.044073* mutant and wild-type CC-1690 (Sager 21 gr) strains. Growth phenotypes on the
 200 amino acids L-serine and L-alanine (8 mM) were imaged after seven days. A control without any
 201 supplemented nitrogen source was included (-N). Growth on ammonium (8 mM NH₄Cl) was tested
 202 in the presence and absence of paromomycin (25 μg·mL⁻¹) after four days. CC-5325 is the wild-type
 203 parental strain of the *lao1* *LMJ.RY0402.044073* mutant. S1-13 are representative random segregants of
 204 the genetic cross between the *lao1* mutant and wild-type CC-1690 strains. **These results represent one**
 205 **of at least three different experiments.**

206 The ability of *C. reinhardtii* to use the 20 proteinogenic amino acids and several di- and tri-peptides
 207 as a sole nitrogen source was assessed (Figure 3). We selected peptides that result in positive
 208 respiratory activity (LA, FA and LG₃) and one (G₃) that does not (Chaiboonchoe et al., 2014), with the
 209 idea that respiration is likely closely linked to the ability to use the peptide for growth. *C. reinhardtii*
 210 growth was analyzed at 4 and 12 days. At 12 days, cultures were evaluated for positive or negative
 211 growth (Figure 3B, C). At 4 days (Figure 3A), cell number was also quantified in order to relate the
 212 efficiency of growth with the LAO1 activity reported for each amino acid (Vallon et al., 1993). We
 213 observed three different phenotypes for growth: LAO1-independent, LAO1-dependent, and no
 214 growth.

215
 216 **Figure 3.** *C. reinhardtii* growth on amino acids and peptides as sole nitrogen source. (A) Short-term
 217 growth on L-amino acids (4 days). (*) From left to right, amino acids are arranged from higher to
 218 lower LAO1-specific activity, previously reported (Vallon et al., 1993). Long-term growth (12 days)
 219 on L-amino acids (B) and di-/tri-peptides (C). Parental *lao1*⁺ strain CC-5325 and the derived *lao1*
 220 mutant (*LMJ.RY0402.044073*) were grown on each amino acids or peptides as the sole nitrogen source
 221 (8 mM, except for L-Tyr: 2 mM) in TAP liquid media. Q: L-glutamine; F: L-phenylalanine; S: L-serine;
 222 M: L-methionine; K: L-lysine; L: L-leucine; N: L-asparagine; A: L-alanine; I: L-isoleucine; R: L-
 223 arginine; W: L-tryptophan; Y: L-tyrosine; V: L-valine; H: L-histidine; D: L-aspartic acid; E: L-glutamic
 224 acid; T: L-threonine; G: glycine; P: L-proline; C: L-cysteine; LA: L-leucyl-alanine; FA: L-phenylalanyl-
 225 alanine; LG₂: L-leucyl-glycyl-glycine; G₃: glycyl-glycyl-glycine. Error bars represent standard deviation
 226 (n=3).

227 LAO1-independent growth was evident for L-arginine (Figure 1B). A specific transporter for L-
 228 arginine likely enables the intracellular processing of this amino acid (Kirk and Kirk, 1978a). Although
 229 the molecular identification of this arginine transporter has not yet been determined, the *C. reinhardtii*
 230 genome encodes six APC (Amino acid Polyamine organoCation) transporters and among them,
 231 AOC5 has been suggested as a candidate (Vallon and Spalding, 2009).

232 Strict LAO1-dependent growth was observed for 16 amino acids, 15 of which are known
 233 substrates for LAO1 (L-glutamine, L-alanine, L-phenylalanine, L-serine, L-asparagine, L-leucine, L-
 234 methionine, L-valine, L-lysine, L-tyrosine, L-histidine, L-isoleucine, L-threonine, L-tryptophan, and
 235 glycine). Consistent with the lower specific activity of LAO1 for some L-amino acids (L-histidine, L-

236 aspartic acid, L-glutamic acid, L-threonine and glycine) (Vallon et al., 1993), slower growth was also
237 observed (12 days, Figure 3A and B). L-cysteine showed a utilization defect in the *lao1* mutant,
238 suggesting that LAO1 is involved in L-cysteine-dependent growth (Figure 3A). L-cysteine is not
239 deaminated by LAO1 but can be spontaneously oxidized in aqueous solution to form the dimer
240 cystine (Kendall and Nord, 1926), which is then efficiently deaminated by LAO1 (Vallon et al., 1993).

241 The LAO1-dependent growth was also observed for some di- and tri-peptides. The use of
242 peptides as nitrogen source by *C. reinhardtii* has not been extensively studied. Vallon et al. (1993)
243 reported that purified LAO1 enzyme is not active on di-peptides, although the di-peptides tested were
244 not specified. A high-throughput screen based on cellular respiration of *C. reinhardtii* in response to a
245 large array of metabolites has shown that *C. reinhardtii* is metabolically active on a number of di- and
246 tri-peptides (108 out of 267 di-peptides, and 3 out of 14 tri-peptides) (Chaiboonchoe et al., 2014).
247 Whether these peptides are nitrogen sources for *C. reinhardtii* growth is unknown, however. We tested
248 three respiration-positive (L-Leu-Ala, L-Phe-Ala and L-Leu-Gly-Gly) and one respiration-negative
249 (Gly-Gly-Gly) peptides (Chaiboonchoe et al., 2014). Peptides that showed a respiration-positive
250 phenotype supported growth of the *lao+* *C. reinhardtii* parental strain CC-5325, while the respiration-
251 negative Gly-Gly-Gly tri-peptide did not (Figure 3C). The *lao1* mutant was unable to grow using these
252 peptides (Figure 3C). These data suggest that LAO1 has a role in peptide assimilation, either by
253 deaminating the peptide directly or via deamination of free amino acids generated through the
254 activity of some extracellular peptidase.

255 *C. reinhardtii* does not grow on L-proline, consistent with the absence of activity of the LAO1
256 enzyme on this amino acid. Recently, it has been shown that a specific mutualistic interaction
257 *Chlamydomonas-Methylobacterium aquaticum* results in metabolic complementation and algal growth
258 on proline (Calatrava et al., 2018). This mutualism on L-proline is the consequence of the amino acid
259 mineralization by *M. aquaticum* producing ammonium that is assimilated by *C. reinhardtii*. In return,
260 *C. reinhardtii* produces glycerol as a result of photosynthetic carbon fixation, which is used by the
261 bacteria. The interaction of *Chlamydomonas* with different *Methylobacterium* spp. also results in algal
262 growth on peptides that *Chlamydomonas* can not use by itself (Calatrava et al., 2018).

263 LAO1 seems to endow *C. reinhardtii* with the advantage of scavenging nitrogen from a broad
264 range of L-amino acids and peptides. Given the impact on algal growth and potential ecological
265 relevance of these results, we investigated the occurrence of LAAO genes in other algal genomes.

266 267 3.2 LAO1 gene expression is down-regulated by the presence of inorganic nitrogen

268 In *C. reinhardtii*, the uptake activity of L-arginine is inhibited by ammonium and nitrate but
269 induced by the absence of nitrogen (Kirk and Kirk, 1978a; Strijkert et al., 1971). Likewise, LAO1 activity
270 is inhibited by ammonium and induced by nitrogen starvation (Vallon et al., 1993). We examined the
271 transcriptional activity of the *LAO1* gene after 10 hours of incubation with inorganic nitrogen sources
272 ammonium, nitrite, or and nitrate (Figure 4). The presence of any of these nitrogen compounds
273 repressed *LAO1* gene expression *C. reinhardtii* seems to prioritize the use of inorganic nitrogen sources
274 over amino acids, the latter likely to be more energetically costly to assimilate.

275
 276 Figure 4. *LAO1* gene expression in the presence of replete extracellular inorganic nitrogen. *C.*
 277 *reinhardtii* was cultured in ammonium-containing media, harvested, rinsed free of ammonium and
 278 transferred to medium supplemented with 4 mM of the inorganic nitrogen sources indicated and
 279 cultivated for 10 hours. NH₄⁺: as ammonium chloride; NO₂⁻: as potassium nitrite; NO₃⁻: as potassium
 280 nitrate; -N: without any nitrogen. Gene expression is shown relative to that of a housekeeping gene,
 281 ubiquitin ligase (González-Ballester et al., 2004). Error bars represent standard deviation (n=3).
 282

283 3.3 LAAO genes occurrence in algal genomes

284 Two genes in the *C. reinhardtii* genome, *LAO1* and *LAO3*, encode for proteins that share 59%
 285 sequence identity. Other sequenced genomes of closely related green algae such as *Volvox* and
 286 *Ostreococcus* do not contain LAAO genes (Vallon and Spalding, 2009). We queried several genome
 287 databases (see *Material and Methods* section) with the *LAO1* protein sequence via reciprocal BLASTp
 288 to identify potential orthologs using the following criteria: (a) translated protein size of 400-600 amino
 289 acid residues; (b) sequence identity greater than 20%; and (c) sequence coverage greater than 60%.
 290 The resulting protein hits were subsequently used in tBLASTn queries against *C. reinhardtii* genome
 291 to identify reciprocal best-hits to confirm *LAO1* orthology. No *LAO1* orthologs satisfying these
 292 criteria were found in other Viridiplantae members, including other closely related green algae like
 293 *Dunaliella* and *Coccomyxa*, and land plants. *LAO1* orthologs are also absent among five other currently
 294 available genomes in the *Chlamydomonas* genus (*C. eustigma*, *C. sphaeroides*, *C. debaryana*, *C. asymmetrica*
 295 and *C. applanata*) (Hirooka et al., 2017).

296 We identified *LAO1* orthologs in 10 out of 27 algal species: *Porphyra umbilicalis*, *Gracilariopsis*
 297 *lemaniformis* and *Chondrus crispus* (Rhodophyta), *Vitrella brassicaformis* (Alveolata), *Aureococcus*
 298 *anophagefferens* and *Pelagophyceae* sp. CCMP2097 (Heterokonta), *Paolovales* sp. CCMP2436, *Emiliana*
 299 *huxleyi* and *Chrysochromulina* sp. CCMP291 (Haptophyta), and *Symbiodinium microadriaticum*
 300 (Dinophyta). These algae appear to have a single *LAO1* ortholog, except for the diatom *Emiliana*
 301 *huxleyi* that seems to have two and the red alga *Porphyra umbilicalis* that has four.

302 To understand the evolutionary history of these algal *LAO1* orthologs, we constructed a
 303 phylogenetic tree along with other LAAO proteins previously analyzed by Campillo-Brocal et al.
 304 (Campillo-Brocal et al., 2015) (Table S1). Fungal, gastropod and vertebrate LAAO members, as well
 305 as other distantly related amine oxidases were included: D-amino acid oxidases (DAAOs), LodA (L-
 306 Lysine ε-oxidase)-like proteins, L-aspartate oxidases (LASPOs) and other enzymes with

307 experimentally reported amine oxidase activity (Campillo-Brocal et al., 2015). Algal protein sequences
308 identified as LAO1 orthologs cluster on the same branch that we named as “ALAAO” (Algal LAAO,
309 Figure 5). This ALAAO branch is distinct in lineage from fungal, gastropods and vertebrates LAAOs.
310 In addition, two bacterial LAAOs from *Oceanobacter kriegii* and *Aquabacterium* sp. NJ1 were included
311 in the phylogenetic analysis since they were found to be LAO1 orthologs according to our criteria.
312 These two LAAOs did not cluster on the same branch as ALAAOs, however, suggesting that ALAAOs
313 may have evolved separately instead of having been acquired through a recent lateral gene transfer
314 event (Figure 5).

315 Within this new ALAAO branch, the sequence identity between LAO1 and other ALAAOs was
316 low (from 23-31% of identity), although this is consistent with previously reported data in LAAO
317 proteins within similar groups (Nuutinen et al., 2012). Nevertheless, conserved motifs in the
318 substrate- and FAD- binding domains are present (Feliciano et al., 2017) (Supplementary Figure S1).

319 Although our data support LAO1 and LAO3 being grouped together within the ALAAOs, their
320 origin is puzzling since we could find no other orthologs within the green algal lineage. We analyzed
321 the genomic context of these genes in hopes of shedding light onto the possible evolutionary history
322 of *C. reinhardtii* ALAAO genes. Immediately adjacent to *LAO1* is the *LAO2* gene (Vallon et al., 1993)
323 that codes for a putative RidA (Reactive intermediate/imine deaminase A) protein (Lambrecht et al.,
324 2012). When *LAO2/RidA* was queried, the most closely related gene was found in cyanobacteria and
325 interestingly, resides adjacent to a putative amine oxidase (*AO*) gene, as previously reported for other
326 bacteria (Niehaus et al., 2015). However, this putative *AO* gene shows low sequence identity to *LAO1*
327 but is a better match to other putative amine oxidases in *C. reinhardtii* (e.g., *AOF2*, *Cre10.g447767.t1.1*)
328 (Figure 6). In contrast to *LAO1* and *LAO3*, *AOF2* shows orthologs in most genomes within the green
329 and red algal lineages, as well as in cyanobacteria (indicated as *AOs* in Figure 7) and did not cluster
330 in the same ALAAO branch in our Maximum Likelihood analysis (Figure 5), suggesting that the
331 *AOF/AO* family may have given rise to ALAAOs.

339
 340 **Figure 6.** Amine oxidase-*RidA* synteny analysis between the green alga *C. reinhardtii* and the
 341 cyanobacterium *Gloeocapsa* sp. PCC7428. AOF2 (Phytozome ID *Cre10.g447767.t1.1*); AO, putative
 342 amino acid oxidase (NCBI ID no. *AFZ32287.1*); *RidA*, Reactive intermediate/imine deaminase A family
 343 gene (NCBI ID no. *AFZ32287.1*); *LAO1* (NCBI ID no. *AAB97101.1*); *LAO2/RidA* (NCBI ID no.
 344 *AAB97101.1*); *LAO3* (NCBI ID no. *EDP07010.1*). 'E' refers to the expectation values obtained by
 345 pairwise alignment at the protein level. The circular arrow below the AO gene indicates a reversed
 346 orientation of the *C. reinhardtii* *LAO1* gene adjacent to the *RidA* ortholog relative to that seen in
 347 cyanobacteria.
 348

AA = Archaeplastidan ancestor

349
 350 **Figure 7.** Comparative genomic analysis of algal LAAOs. ALAAO, putative algal L-amino acid oxidase
 351 genes found in this work; AO, putative amine oxidase ortholog to AOF2 family in *C. reinhardtii*; RidA,
 352 putative reactive intermediate/imine deaminase A family genes. Orthologs of the amine oxidase (AO)
 353 adjacent to RidA in the cyanobacterium *Gloeocapsa* sp. was included since this organism had the most
 354 closely matching RidA ortholog to LAO2 of *C. reinhardtii*. The dotted arrow indicates the primary
 355 endosymbiosis event in which a protist engulfed a cyanobacterium and led to the archaeplastidan
 356 ancestor (AA). Dotted lines connecting gene boxes indicate that these genes are not adjacent to each
 357 other in currently available genome assemblies.

358 No LAO2/RidA ortholog was found in any other algal genome. This gene may have been lost in
 359 most algal lineages but uniquely retained in *C. reinhardtii*, or *C. reinhardtii* may have acquired it via
 360 lateral gene transfer. Given the currently available genomes and genome assemblies, our phylogenetic
 361 analysis favours the idea that ALAAOs may have a common origin in an archaeplastidan ancestor
 362 that was the result of a primary endosymbiosis of a protist engulfing a free cyanobacterium. We
 363 propose that the presence of ALAAO genes in the red algal lineage and the thus far unique co-
 364 occurrence of ALAAO-RidA genes in *C. reinhardtii* (LAO1-LAO2/RidA) may be due to gene duplication
 365 and divergence events in the ancestral archaeplastida, with further loss of RidA gene in the red lineage
 366 and loss of the ALAAO-RidA cluster in the green algae (except for *C. reinhardtii*) (Supplementary
 367 Figure S2). Alternatively, an ALAAO-RidA cluster from a microbe related to the ancestral
 368 archaeplastida may have been laterally transferred to *C. reinhardtii*. Nevertheless, future genome
 369 sequences and reassemblies are crucial to reveal the yet uncertain origin of LAAOs in algae.

370
 371

372 3.4 How do algae scavenge nitrogen from amino acids?

373 The use of amino acids by algae may be of eco-physiological importance, and the extracellular
374 localization of ALAAs such as LAO1 could be a strategy for scavenging from exogenous amino
375 acids and peptides. To understand whether this could be a common feature for ALAAs, we
376 examined *in silico* predictions of cellular localization of these ALAAs. Our analysis suggests that 5
377 out of 10 algal species contain putative extracellular LAAs (Table 1), a pattern that indicates that
378 ALAAs could be a general strategy by algae to derive environmental nitrogen. Surveying the
379 literature for reports of algal amino acid uptake, extracellular deamination activity and growth on
380 amino acids (Table 2 and Supplementary Table S2), we synthesize different potential strategies for
381 nitrogen scavenging below.

382 In the green alga *Dunaliella*, four species were recently reported to be unable to use proteinogenic
383 amino acids as a sole nitrogen source, with the exception of L-histidine, which can be transported into
384 the cell (Murphree et al., 2017). In *Volvox carteri*, only L-arginine is the only amino acid transported,
385 although it is not catabolized and therefore not used as nitrogen source (Kirk and Kirk, 1978b). None
386 of these algal genomes contains ALAA (Murphree et al., 2017). This fact, together with the deficiency
387 of transport systems could explain why these algae do not generally grow on most amino acids.

388 In *Chlorella*, growth on a broad range of amino acids and extensive amino acid uptake systems
389 have been reported (Algeus, 1949; Cho and Komor, 1985; Kirk and Kirk, 1978c; Zhang et al., 2015)
390 (Table 2). Interestingly, amino acids have been shown to be supplied to this alga by symbiotic hosts
391 (Kato and Imamura, 2008; McAuley, 1991). Thus, amino acid uptake systems in algae may have been
392 driven and/or retained by nutritional selective advantages provided in association with specific
393 symbiotic partners.

394 Heterokonta algae show different abilities to assimilate nitrogen from amino acids and peptides.
395 *Aureococcus anophagefferens* possesses similar abilities as *C. reinhardtii* to grow on amino acids, and
396 show amino acids uptake as well as extracellular deaminase activities (Mulholland et al., 2002),
397 consistent with a putative extracellular ALAA encoded in its genome (Tables 1, 2). *Phaeodactylum*
398 *tricornutum* grows on a wide range of amino acids, shows amino acid uptake activity for L-arginine
399 and L-lysine, and exhibits extracellular deamination activity for several amino acids (Hayward, 1965;
400 Rees and Allison, 2006); however, we did not find any LAO1 ortholog in the current version of the *P.*
401 *tricornutum* genome. Whether the reported extracellular deaminase activity is due to another amine
402 oxidase enzyme remains to be determined. *Thalassiosira pseudonana* is unable to grow on amino acids
403 as sole nitrogen source (Ietswaart et al., 1994; Palenik and Morel, 1990b) and lacks an ALAA gene.
404 Perhaps the inability of *T. pseudonana* (and *Dunaliella*) to grow amino acids can be complemented by
405 interactions with bacteria that can mineralize these nitrogen sources, similar to what we recently
406 reported for *C. reinhardtii* and *Methylobacterium* spp. (Calatrava et al., 2018).

407

408 **Table 1. ALAAO enzymes and their putative cellular locations.**

Phylum	Species	Natural habitat	Protein ID	DB	Putative cellular location					
					Target	Score				
						Mit	Chl	SP		
Chlorophyta	<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	Freshwater/ soil	AAB97101.1 (LAO1)	NCBI	SP	0.01	0.01	1.64		
			Cre05.g246550.t1.2 (LAO3)	Phytozome	O	0.00	0.62	0.00		
Rhodophyta	<i>Porphyra umbilicalis</i>		OSX78923.1	NCBI	SP	0.12	0.50	0.70		
			OSX73518.1	NCBI	SP	0.00	0.10	1.16		
			OSX78913.1	NCBI	Chl	0.01	1.85	0.21		
			OSX80811.1	NCBI	SP	0.03	1.02	1.41		
			ATE86702.1	NCBI	SP	0.03	0.21	0.21		
Heterokonta	<i>Gracilaropsis lemaneiformis</i>		XP_005713538.1	NCBI	SP	0.08	0.02	1.27		
			<i>Chondrus crispus</i>	Marine waters	jgiPelago2097	JGI	O	0.00	0.01	0.11
			<i>Pelagophyceae</i> sp. CCMP2097		XP_009033458.1	NCBI	SP	0.17	0.02	2.02
			<i>Aureococcus anophagefferens</i>		jgiPavlov2436	JGI	SP	0.17	0.08	1.51
<i>Pavlova</i> sp. CCMP2436	XP_005785782.1	NCBI	Mit		0.50	0.11	0.07			
Haptophyta	<i>Emiliana huxleyi</i>		XP_005777092.1	NCBI	O	0.02	0.00	0.04		
			<i>Chrysochromulina</i> sp. CCMP291	KOO35684.1	NCBI	O	0.18	0.02	0.05	
Alveolata	<i>Vitrella brassicaformis</i>		CEL94447.1	NCBI	O	0.03	0.03	0.05		
Dinophyta	<i>Symbiodinium microadriaticum</i>		OLQ08796.1*	NCBI	O	0.00	0.00	0.00		

409 Putative subcellular location for ALAAO enzymes was determined using the algal-specific subcellular
410 localization prediction tool, PredAlgo program, which computes a score for three cellular
411 compartments: mitochondrion (Mit), chloroplast (Chl), and secretory pathway (SP). For scores below
412 the following cutoffs, the target is indicated as 'other' (O): 0.42 for the mitochondrion, 0.41 for the
413 chloroplast, and 0.14 for the secretion pathway (Tardif et al., 2012). Databases: NCBI
414 (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/>), JGI (<https://jgi.doe.gov/>), and Phytozome
415 (<https://phytozome.jgi.doe.gov/>). *Partial protein sequence.

416

417 **Table 2. Synthesis of literature findings on amino acid utilization by algae.**

	Algal species	Growth	Uptake	Extracellular LAAO activity	Extracellular LAO1 homolog	Ref.
Chlorophyta	<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	+	+	+	AAB97101.1	1, 2, 3, 4, 5
	<i>Chlamydomonas inflexa</i>	+	N.F.	N.F.	N.A.	6
	<i>Chlamydomonas minuta</i>	+	N.F.	N.F.	N.A.	6
	<i>Chlamydomonas moewusii</i>	+	N.F.	N.F.	N.A.	6
	<i>Dunaliella salina</i>	+	+	-	-	7
	<i>Volvox carteri</i>	N.F.	+	N.F.	-	1
	<i>Chlorella pyrenoidosa</i>	+	+	N.F.	N.A.	1, 8
	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	+	+	N.F.	-	9, 10
	<i>Ulva lactuca</i>	N.F.	+	N.F.	N.A.	11
Rhodophyta	<i>Gymnogongrus flabelliformis</i>	N.F.	N.F.	+	N.A.	12
	<i>Amphiora crassissima</i>	N.F.	N.F.	+	N.A.	13
Alveolata	<i>Amphidinium carterae</i>	N.F.	N.F.	+	N.A.	14
	<i>Amphidinium operculatum</i>	+	N.F.	N.F.	N.A.	14
	<i>Symbiodinium microadriaticum</i>	N.F.	N.F.	-	-(intracellular)	14
Heterokonta	<i>Cyclotella cryptica</i>	N.F.	+	N.F.	N.A.	15
	<i>Phaeodactylum tricornutum</i>	+	+	+	-	16, 17
	<i>Aureococcus anophagefferens</i>	+	+	+	XP_009033458.1*	18
	<i>Thalassiosira pseudonana</i>	-	N.F.	N.F.	-	19
	<i>Thalassiosira weissflogii</i>	N.F.	N.F.	-	N.A.	14
	<i>Pleurochrysis carterae</i>	+	N.F.	+	N.A.	14
Haptophyta	<i>Pleurochrysis scherfelli</i>	N.F.	N.F.	+	N.A.	14
	<i>Pleurochrysis sp.</i>	N.F.	N.F.	+	N.A.	14
	<i>Emiliana huxleyi</i>	+	N.F.	-	-(intracellular)	10, 19
	<i>Coccolitus pelagicus</i>	+	N.F.	N.F.	N.A.	20
	<i>Calcidiscus leptoporus</i>	N.F.	N.F.	N.F.	N.A.	20
	<i>Prymnesium parvum</i>	+	N.F.	+	N.A.	14
	<i>Pavlova gyrans</i>	N.F.	N.F.	-	N.A.	14

418 (+) Detected; (-) Not detected; (N.F.) Not Found in the literature; (N.A.) Not Available genome; (*) Putative
419 protein. References: 1, Kirk and Kirk, 1978a; 2, Muñoz-Blanco et al., 1990; 3, Piedras et al., 1992; 4, Vallon et al.,
420 1993; 5, Zuo et al., 2012. 6, Cain, 1965; 7, Murphree et al., 2017; 8, Zhang et al., 2015; 9, Algeus, 1949; 10, Cho and
421 Komor, 1985; 11, Tyler and Macko, 2005; 12, Fujisawa et al., 1982; 13, Ito et al., 1987; 14, Palenik and Morel, 1990a;
422 15, Hellebust, 1978; 16, Rees and Allison, 2006; 17, Hayward, 1965; 18, Mulholland et al., 2002; 19, Ietswaart et
423 al., 1994; 20, Benner and Passow, 2010. Further information can be found in Supplementary Table S2.

424 3.5 Models for nitrogen scavenging from amino acids and peptides in algae

425 The use of organic nitrogen by algal species may be a means of niche partitioning in habitats
426 where these forms may be available and competition for inorganic nitrogen by other organisms is
427 considerable. How algae use amino acids and peptides may be relevant for the dynamics of algal
428 blooms and for biotechnological applications such as bioremediation. Here, we propose three
429 different models based on our data for *C. reinhardtii* and other algae (Figure 8).

430 **Figure 8.** Models for how algae acquire nitrogen from amino acids and/or peptides. **A,**
431 *Chlamydomonas*-like model with: (1) amino acid-specific transport systems, (2) extracellular L-amino
432 acid oxidase(s), and (3) metabolic complementation with bacteria. **B,** *Chlorella*-like model whereby
433 extracellular ALAAO orthologs are missing but there are several amino acid transporter systems. **C,**
434 *Dunaliella*-like model whereby ALAAOs are missing but there is a single amino acid transporter. For
435 all three systems, metabolic complementation by nitrogen mineralizing bacteria may support algal
436 growth.
437

438 In Model A, characterized by *C. reinhardtii*, growth on amino acids and peptides is supported by
439 three different pathways to scavenge nitrogen (Figure 8A). First, amino acids may be transported into
440 the cell and catabolized to provide not only nitrogen but also carbon. For *C. reinhardtii*, this pathway
441 seems to be restricted to a single proteinogenic amino acid, L-arginine (Kirk and Kirk, 1978a). Second,
442 amino acids are deaminated extracellularly to produce ammonium that is then transported into the
443 cell via ammonium transporters (Muñoz-Blanco et al., 1990). This pathway relies on LAO1 orthologs
444 and is effective for most of the proteinogenic amino acids (including L-arginine) and also for di- and
445 tri-peptides. Third, interactions with bacteria may allow metabolic complementation and facilitate
446 algal growth on amino acids and peptides that are not transported or deaminated (Calatrava et al.,
447 2018; Ietswaart et al., 1994).

448 In Model B, characterized by *Chlorella* spp., many different amino acid transporters are
449 responsible for growth on amino acids (Figure 8 B). *Chlorella* spp. possess at least seven transport
450 systems responsible for the uptake of most of amino acids (Bong-Heuy Cho and Ewald Komor, 1983;
451 Sauer and Tanner, 1985). In contrast, only single transporter systems have been reported for
452 *Chlamydomonas*, *Volvox*, and *Dunaliella* (Murphree et al., 2017; Kirk and Kirk, 1978a, 1978b). This broad
453 amino acid uptake strategy does not appear to be a common strategy among algae. In Model C, neither
454 deamination or uptake are effective for algal growth (Figure 8 C). Thus, metabolic complementation
455 by nitrogen-mineralizing organisms may be the only effective pathway to grow on extracellular
456 amino acids and peptides.

457 These different models for amino acid nitrogen scavenging likely reflect the evolutionary
458 histories of adaptation of these algae to the natural environment and/or biotic partners. For example,
459 strains of *Chlorella* that form symbioses with other organisms appear to be highly adapted for growth
460 on amino acids and are unable to use nitrate; free-living strains, in contrast, appear to be better
461 adapted for growth on inorganic nitrogen sources (Quispe et al., 2016). The poor ability of *Dunaliella*
462 spp. to use amino acids as a source of nitrogen may be a reflection of them occupying niches where
463 inorganic nitrogen is commonly available (Murphree et al., 2017) but free amino acids are not. The
464 ability to scavenge nitrogen from amino acids may have been an ancestral trait that was lost due to
465 relaxed selection. Having an extracellular LAAO is an unusual trait among green algae and suggests
466 that it confers *C. reinhardtii* with an adaptive advantage in the nutrient-rich, disturbed soils this alga
467 typically inhabits (Sasso et al., 2018). In such contexts, we surmise that extracellular deamination may
468 be a better ecological strategy than relying on a broad amino acid uptake system. Since *C. reinhardtii*
469 does not use resulting keto acids released by LAAO activity (Muñoz-Blanco et al., 1990), these carbon
470 skeletons may be key in cooperative C-N exchange interactions with bacteria that lead to enhanced
471 mutual growth on amino acids (Calatrava et al., 2018); keto acids may also play a role in
472 chelating/solubilizing iron and/or buffering the effects of hydrogen peroxide (Drechsel et al., 1993;
473 Kim et al., 2016).

474 Given the prevalence of algae-bacteria co-occurrences and reported mutualistic interactions in
475 nature (Ashen and Goff, 2000; Bruckner et al., 2008; Gärdes et al., 2011; Goecke et al., 2013; Gonzalez
476 and Bashan, 2000; Hernandez et al., 2009), it seems likely that algal-bacterial complementation may
477 be the most common pathway in algae to assimilate nitrogen from amino acids and peptides. It is
478 well-known that many algae are difficult to cultivate under laboratory conditions, which is most likely
479 due to a failure to recapitulate the requirements provided by other mutualistic microorganisms like
480 bacteria (Ramanan et al., 2015). Our data suggest that a distinct lineage of extracellular LAAO
481 proteins (ALAAOs) is shared among algae in the Chlorophyta, Alveolata, Heterokonta, Haptophyta
482 and Dinophyta. Understanding the function, substrate specificity, localization, occurrence, and
483 evolutionary history of LAAO enzymes will provide a fuller picture of the role of algae and amino
484 acids/peptide substrates in the cycling of nitrogen in natural environments, and may provide useful
485 information for LAAOs biotechnological applications.

486

487 4. Conflict of Interest

488 The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial
489 relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

490

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497

498 6. Author Contributions

499 VC, AG and EH conceived the project and designed the experiments; VC performed the
500 experiments; VC, EH, AL, AG and EF analyzed and discussed the data. VC, AG and EH wrote the
501 paper.

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7. Supplementary Material

Figure S1: LAAO protein multiple sequence alignment. **Figure S2:** Hypothesis for the origin of ALAAO genes. **Table S1:** Protein sequence IDs used for phylogenetic tree construction. **Table S2:** Synthesis of information from the literature on the utilization of amino acids by algae.

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Supplementary Figure S1. LAAO protein multiple sequence alignment. Algal LAAOs (ALAAOs) are highlighted in light yellow. Amino acid residues are highlighted in blue according to percentage of identity. *The LAAO protein sequence for *Symbiodinium microadriaticum* is partial. Alignment was performed using Clustal Omega (REF). All LAAO members from the algal branch contain a GGRX₂[S/T] motif as found in fungal, gastropod and vertebrate LAAOs; this motif is absent in D-amino acid oxidases, LASPOs and LodA-like proteins. Sequences within the FAD-binding domain,

762 particularly those containing the dinucleotide binding domain GXGX₂G and WAEXS[L/V] motifs,
 763 which are highly conserved across LAAOs, were as well present in all ALAAOs. Within the substrate-
 764 binding domain described for the *Bothrops atrox* snake LAAO (Feliciano et al., 2017), a conserved
 765 [D/E]hGAYR sequence ('h' denotes a hydrophobic amino acid) is present in algal members. In algae,
 766 an aromatic tyrosine residue is conserved in this 'h' position, whereas in bacteria, fungi and animals,
 767 a methionine is conserved at this position. Glycine and arginine residues in this substrate binding
 768 domain are generally well conserved except in *Synechococcus elongatus* and in the putative amine
 769 oxidase AOF2 of *C. reinhardtii*.

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 771 **Supplementary Figure S2.** Putative origin of algal LAAO (ALAAO) genes. We propose two possible
 772 explanations; in the ancestral archaeplastidan, prior to red and green lineages diversification: (1) an
 773 *in situ* duplication of the putative archaetypal LAAO (orange boxes) occurred with further divergence
 774 of this copy towards ALAAO (red boxes) and genetic decoupling of AO and ALAAO loci; or (2) a
 775 duplication of the AO-RidA cluster with AO divergence to ALAAO with a subsequent loss of the
 776 adjacent RidA (blue boxes) in the duplicated ALAAO cluster. The RidA gene and ALAAO-RidA cluster
 777 may have been lost in the red and green lineages, respectively, but retained in *C. reinhardtii*.
 778 Alternatively, lateral gene transfer of an AO-RidA cluster from an ancestral archaeplastidan-related
 779 microbe to *C. reinhardtii* may have occurred (not shown in the figure).
 780